

PYROLYSIS PROCESS

Fig 10: Plastic Bottle Collection

Fig 11: Loading the Pyrolysis Chamber

Fig 12: Heating Process

Fig 13: Gas Flow & Condensation

- **Pyrolysis process:** Pyrolysis is a thermal decomposition of plastic waste in the absence of oxygen, converting it into useful products like oil, gas, and char.
- **Energy recovery:** The process recycles plastic into fuel, offering an alternative energy source and reducing reliance on fossil fuels.
- **Eco-friendly disposal:** Pyrolysis helps manage plastic waste sustainably by minimizing landfill use and reducing environmental pollution.

Fig 14: Extracted Oil